

4D-WORKS: Development of a Topographic 4D STAC Extension (topo4d) for Curating and Cataloging Multi-Source Geospatial Time Series Datasets

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¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

Abstract

Spatiotemporal analysis of geospatial time series data has gained increasing attention with the emergence of 4D point clouds and automatic acquisition technologies such as permanent laser scanning (PLS), time-lapse photogrammetry, and uncrewed aerial vehicle (UAV) platforms, enabling near-continuous in-situ monitoring of Earth surface dynamics for change detection and process characterization. However, facing massive data volumes through the temporal domain, current topographic data curation practices often rely on empirically determined processing and management, which may significantly affect reusability, interoperability, and hence processing efficiency due to the absence or heterogeneous nature of metadata. The need for standardized approaches to manage time-dependent metadata has become critical as the demands for sharing data and reproducing analysis across tools and application domains increase. We propose a topographic 4D extension (topo4d) to the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) framework, which provides an open and extensible specification for automatic metadata curation and FAIR data management practices. The deliverables include a comprehensive guide, open-access repository, template notebooks, a tutorial workshop and scientific dissemination about developed best practices, demonstrating how the topo4d extension facilitates the interoperability and reusability of 4D datasets and presenting the corresponding metadata curation workflows applied to two real-world environmental monitoring applications. This pilot advances research data management (RDM) workflows to fully consider the special properties of 3D time series (4D topographic data) and makes them accessible to the wider user community, i.e., researchers and practitioners from Earth System Sciences and public and private organizations working in environmental monitoring contexts. The future directions may draw attention from different domain communities (e.g., from geomorphology, hydrology, ecology) to make consistent and transparent rules for curating metadata, which is important for maintaining semantic clarity and reproducibility.

I. Introduction

The rapid growth of high-frequency Earth observation, ranging from multi-temporal to time series and near-continuous (so-called 4D) acquisitions, acquired from satellites, airplanes or uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs), and ground-based platforms, has created great opportunities for monitoring Earth surface dynamics induced by environmental processes or anthropogenic activity. These observations include point clouds (e.g., from photogrammetry or LiDAR), imagery (e.g., optical or radar), and end products (e.g., terrain models, orthomosaic images, or change maps). However, the complexity and diversity of these data often create barriers between data providers, curators, and users to interact effectively. This becomes especially pronounced in handling and analyzing dense topographic time series, as acquired, for example, through permanent laser scanning (PLS) (Lindenbergh et al., 2025) or time-lapse photogrammetry (Eltner et al., 2017). In particular, the lack of standards for time-dependent metadata, formats, and interfaces poses challenges to the *Interoperability* and *Reusability* as central components of FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Although the community increasingly publishes open-access topographic 4D datasets, such as Kijkduin (Vos et al., 2022), Mariakerke (Vos et al., 2024), Noordwijk (Vos et al., 2023), Helheim Glacier (Shahin et al., 2025), and Schneeferner (Anders et al., 2023), metadata practices remain heterogeneous across repositories and disciplines. Information is often scattered across LAS/LAZ headers, auxiliary PDF or TXT files, customized formats, or separate per-epoch documents, leading to fragmented and tool-specific data organization. More integrated catalog-based approaches, such as the GeoJSON design of LiPheStream (Wittke et al., 2024), demonstrate the advantages of machine-readable metadata for efficient querying and cross-repository interoperability, but such solutions are not yet common practice. Fragmentation also persists within processing software, where tools typically support only partial metadata relevant to their own workflows, without providing a holistic, multi-source, temporally aware metadata framework.

Existing standards such as ISO 19115 (Kresse & Fadaie, 2004), OGC specifications (Kamel Boulos et al., 2011), and the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2018) provide a foundation for structured spatiotemporal metadata, but they lack support for complex temporal relationships essential for 4D topographic datasets, for example, per-epoch alignment parameters and processing details. Therefore, this pilot introduces the *topo4d* STAC extension: a machine-readable, interoperable schema designed specifically for multi-source topographic 4D datasets, which enable explicit handling of time-dependent information, and is coupled with an automated curation workflow for harvesting, structuring, and publishing metadata. Together, these contributions establish a standardized and scalable approach for curating and cataloging multi-source 4D datasets and demonstrate its application in real-world environmental monitoring scenarios.

II. Results

a) Implemented Solution

Our solution includes: (1) the topo4d STAC extension² is openly developed and documented on GitHub, (2) the curation workflow is presented through GitHub pages³ with (3) real-world environment monitoring scenarios, (4) web-based metadata templates, and (5) example usage notebooks on how to create catalogs from raw data and how to use catalogs within existing technique stacks, e.g., python-based point cloud time series processing package py4dgeo (Bernhard Höfle et al., 2025). The complete solution has been compiled into a full paper (Wang et al., in review) submitted to the ISPRS Congress 2026⁴ by the date this report is submitted. The external link to the publication will be updated on the project page once available.

topo4D STAC Extension

The STAC specification defines a standardized framework for describing and cataloging spatio-temporal assets that capture information about the Earth within a certain range of spatial and temporal scales (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2018). Building on STAC's native support for extensions, our proposed topo4d extension introduces additional fields to represent time-dependent metadata in topographic time series datasets. It defines a JSON schema that captures the essential metadata elements relevant to 4D topographic observations. This schema extends the STAC standard by incorporating attributes such as acquisition settings, processing parameters, uncertainty metrics, and alignment transformations, ensuring interoperability with other STAC-compliant ecosystems. Particularly, the topo4d extension ensures that time-dependent metadata are not treated as temporary annotations but as first-class, schema-defined fields. This structured metadata enables automatic validation and improves queryability.

Existing 4D topographic observation metadata can be mapped to topo4d-specific fields in a catalog according to the extension schema. In particular, two essential object fields *topo4d:trafometa* and *topo4d:productmeta* are defined:

- *topo4d:trafometa* contains multi-epoch alignment metadata, including co-registration transformation, registration error, and reference epoch, e.g., parameters computed by ICP or its variants (Besl & McKay, 1992; Yang & Holst, 2025).
- *topo4d:productmeta* describes processing-related information, such as product type, algorithm parameters, data source, and product level. It is primarily used when the asset represents a derived product, such as a digital elevation model, orthomosaic image, mesh, quantitative change information or other thematic outputs.

The proposed topo4d extension provides a comprehensive metadata schema specifying all relevant fields accessible to different tools and processing steps, thereby ensuring interoperability

² <https://github.com/tum-rsa/topo4d>

³ <https://tum-rsa.github.io/4D-WORKS/>

⁴ <https://www.isprs2026toronto.com/call-for-submissions>

and completeness in managing multi-source topographic 4D datasets across tools and pipelines.

Metadata Curation Workflow

The proposed metadata curation workflow follows a three-layer architecture connecting raw data sources to a FAIR topographic 4D dataset (Figure 1). At the "Metadata Layer", we harmonize heterogeneous metadata from hosting repositories, local archives, and file headers into a unified dictionary, providing a consistent representation of common, acquisition, processing, time-dependent, and assets information. At the "topo4d Layer", we leverage the STAC structure to transform these harvested metadata into standardized entities, following the proposed topo4d extension. This layer ensures semantic consistency, machine readability, and temporal traceability of 4D datasets by organizing items, collections, and catalogs hierarchically. Finally, the "User Layer" enables publication and interaction with the curated dataset through STAC APIs or web interfaces, supporting automated search, filtering, and integration with the external systems (e.g., visualization tools, analysis pipelines). Together, these three layers establish a transparent and interoperable workflow that bridges data campaigns, metadata curation, and user interaction. The workflow ensures that FAIR principles are followed while handling complex research metadata for topographic 4D datasets across Earth system science disciplines.

Figure 1 Three-layer architecture of the metadata curation for topographic 4D datasets using the topo4d STAC extension.

Real-world Environment Monitoring Scenarios

We showcase two catalogs organizing (1) a multi-source multi-temporal dataset, and (2) a near-continuous 3D time series dataset.

The first catalog integrates data acquired at the Isar riverbed site, a dynamic braided riverbed shaped by sediment transport and human intervention through upstream discharge control at a weir. It is located in Southern Germany, at a natural reserve region of the Alpine Isar river

(WGS84: 47.5301°N, 11.3090°E) (Figure 2). The 3D point clouds were acquired using a DJI Phantom 4 RTK (photogrammetry) and a DJI M350 RTK carrying a Zenmuse L2 LiDAR sensor (laser scanning) during repeated surveys from August 2024 to September 2025 (four epochs at seasonal intervals). Point clouds were processed via Multi-View Stereo reconstruction in Pix4Dmatic (photogrammetry) and LiDAR data was processed in DJI Terra. Topographic surface changes were quantified using the established M3C2 algorithm (Lague et al., 2013). Surface change values are stored as attributes per point coordinate of the reference point cloud in separate files. Complementary PlanetScope imagery from August to November 2024 was retrieved from PSScene⁵, providing high-frequency optical observations at daily to weekly intervals that enable near-continuous monitoring of short-term events such as high-discharge periods. All datasets were georeferenced in WGS 84 / UTM Zone 32N (EPSG: 32632) and stored in open formats (GeoTIFF for imagery, LAS/LAZ for point clouds⁶) with accompanying survey documentation.

We organize all data sources into a multi-source, multi-temporal Isar Riverbed catalog, integrating three collections: (1) UAV point clouds of different sources at multiple epochs, (2) change layers derived from bitemporal point clouds, and (3) satellite imagery time series. It provides a hierarchical structure that connects point clouds, change layers (i.e., analysis products), and imagery time series over space and time, enabling seamless cross-querying between data sources.

Figure 2 Catalog visualization of the Isar riverbed site, Wallgau, Germany (WGS84 / UTM 32N). The red bounding box shows the spatial extent of PlanetScope imagery, and the blue bounding box delineates the spatial extent of UAV point clouds and surface change products derived from

⁵ <https://docs.planet.com/data/imagery/planetscope/psscene/>

⁶ https://rsa-viewer.lrg.tum.de/scenes/Isar_Riverbank.html

3D change analysis. The bottom plot visualizes the temporal availability of different data sources.

The second catalog example organizes a 3D point cloud time series dataset was acquired by a PLS setup at Kijkduin sandy beach, The Netherlands (WGS84: 52.0705°N, 4.2194°E) during the winter of 2016 - 2017 (Vos et al., 2022). A Riegl VZ-2000 laser scanner mounted on a stable frame overlooking the beach recorded hourly point clouds with densities ranging from 2 to 20 points/m². The resulting 2,942 epochs spanning six months were published in the PANGAEA data repository. The 4D dataset demonstrates great value in spatiotemporal analysis for surface dynamics, such as surface dynamics extraction (Anders et al., 2021; Kuschnerus et al., 2021) and characterization (Wang & Anders, 2025).

To render the available metadata interoperable across tools, workflows, and applications, we extract and curate a one-month subset of the full dataset to provide an example STAC collection within the catalog using the topo4d extension. The curated collection includes 1,019 epochs spanning from January to February 2017, and can be interacted with a web-based tool, e.g., STAC Browser⁷ (Figure 3).

Kijkduin TLS Point Clouds Collection

Description
Kijkduin TLS Point Clouds Collection
A collection of point cloud from Kijkduin Sandy Beach, The Netherlands.

License CC-BY 4.0
Temporal Extent 2017-01-17 12:00:41 UTC - 2017-02-28 23:01:12 UTC

Provider
TU Delft

Metadata
General
Num Items: 1019
Count: 1019
Timestamp List:
List:
- 2017-01-17 12:00:41
- 2017-01-17 13:00:42
- 2017-01-17 14:00:43

Items (1019) [Ascending] [Descending]

kijkduin_170117_120041 COPC 2017-01-17 12:00:41 UTC	kijkduin_170121_060051 COPC 2017-01-21 06:00:51 UTC
kijkduin_170117_130042 COPC 2017-01-17 13:00:42 UTC	kijkduin_170121_070051 COPC 2017-01-21 07:00:51 UTC
kijkduin_170117_140043 COPC 2017-01-17 14:00:43 UTC	kijkduin_170121_080051 COPC 2017-01-21 08:00:51 UTC
kijkduin_170117_150043 COPC 2017-01-17 15:00:43 UTC	kijkduin_170121_090052 COPC 2017-01-21 09:00:52 UTC
kijkduin_170117_160044 COPC 2017-01-17 16:00:44 UTC	kijkduin_170121_100053 COPC 2017-01-21 10:00:53 UTC
kijkduin_170117_170045 COPC 2017-01-17 17:00:45 UTC	kijkduin_170121_110054 COPC 2017-01-21 11:00:54 UTC

Figure 3 The collection of a Kijkduin 3D time series subset of one month is visualized via the STAC Browser.

Web-based Metadata Template

Inspired by *mlm-form*⁸, we build a web-based metadata form for the topo4d extension (Figure 4). It allows users to host a user-friendly online template to create and validate topo4d STAC Item metadata for individual data asset.

⁷ <https://github.com/radianteearth/stac-browser>

⁸ <https://github.com/wherobots/mlm-form>

Topo4D Metadata Form

[Reset](#)
[Copy JSON](#)
[Download JSON](#)
[Upload LAS/LAZ](#)
[Topo4D Form](#)
[Asset Form](#)

The [Topographic 4D](#) (Topo4D) metadata specification makes it easy to describe the time-dependent metadata in diverse 4D datasets (time series of 3D geographic data) and enable search and discovery under STAC ecosystem. Please complete all required fields below and in the Asset Form prior to copying or downloading the JSON result. Downloaded JSONs will be stored in your download directory and named based on Item Name field. For more information on the specification, refer to the [Topo4D documentation](#).

Item Name

* Datetime (ISO8601)

* Data Type

Timezone

```
{
  "type": "Feature",
  "stac_version": "1.1.0",
  "stac_extensions": [
    "https://tum-rsa.github.io/topo4d/v0.1.0/schema.json"
  ],
  "id": "Isar_20240812_UPH_10cm",
  "geometry": {
    "type": "Polygon",
    "coordinates": [
      [
        [
          11.316376321608464,
          47.5263767376331
        ],
        [
          11.316376321608464,
          47.53158992125014
        ],
        [
          11.304866670963863,
          47.53158992125014
        ],
        [
          11.304866670963863,
          47.5263767376331
        ],
        [
          11.316376321608464,
          47.5263767376331
        ]
      ]
    ]
  }
}
```

Figure 4 A web-based form provides a JSON-format topo4d STAC metadata template that is responsive to user's inputs.

Example Usage Notebooks

Practical examples for these two catalogs and usage scripts in the form of Jupyter Notebooks (Figure 5) are provided with the topo4d GitHub repository, demonstrating how the catalog becomes a living repository of topographic 4D datasets.

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Builder Utilities

Create more items

After confirming the helpers work for a single file we scale up to the full dataset. The loop below merges in the shared user metadata for each LAS file, builds a list of Items, and assigns self HREFs so they can be written to disk later on.

```
In [ ]: def item_from_metadata(metadata: Dict[str, Any]) -> pystac.Item:
    item_id = get_id(metadata)
    item_datetime = get_datetime(metadata)
    item_geo = get_geo(metadata)

    item = pystac.Item(
        id=item_id,
        geometry=item_geo["geometry"],
        bbox=item_geo["bbox"],
        datetime=item_datetime.replace(tzinfo=None),
        properties={}
    )

    # Add standard STAC extensions
    item.stac_extensions.extend([
        "https://stac-extensions.github.io/projection/v2.0.0/schema.json",
        "https://stac-extensions.github.io/pointcloud/v2.0.0/schema.json",
        "https://stac-extensions.github.io/timestamps/v1.1.0/schema.json"
    ])

    # Apply topo4d extension
    topo4d_ext = Topo4DExtension.ext(item, add_if_missing=True)
    topo4d_ext.tz = metadata.get("timezone", "UTC")
    topo4d_ext.data_type = DataType(metadata.get("data_type", "pointcloud"))
    topo4d_ext.acquisition_mode = metadata.get("acquisition_mode", None) # Fixed
    topo4d_ext.orientation = metadata.get("orientation", None)
    topo4d_ext.spatial_resolution = metadata.get("spatial_resolution", None)
    topo4d_ext.positional_accuracy = metadata.get("positional_accuracy", None)

    # Use standard STAC extensions for formerly topo4d properties
    item.properties["pro:code"] = item_geo.get("native_crs", None)
    item.properties["instruments"] = [metadata.get("sensor")] if metadata.get("sa
    item.properties["pc:count"] = metadata.get("header", {}).get("point_count", 0)
    item.properties["pc:type"] = "lidar" if metadata.get("acquisition_mode") == "

    # Add timestamps if available
    if metadata.get("header", {}).get("creation_date"):
        try:
            creation_date = datetime.strptime(metadata["header"]["creation_date"]
```

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Figure 5 A screenshot of one of the notebooks presented in 4D-WORKS online documentation

b) Data and Software availability

The project resources are accessible through the main project page at <https://www.asg.ed.tum.de/rsa/forschung/4d-works>, which serves as the main entry point. The topo4d STAC extension is openly available in the GitHub repository <https://github.com/tum-rsa/topo4d>, and its JSON schema (<https://tum-rsa.github.io/topo4d/v0.2.0/schema.json>) is published via GitHub Pages for direct reference and validation. Complementing this, the 4D-WORKS online guide is hosted on GitHub Pages at <https://tum-rsa.github.io/4D-WORKS/>, providing comprehensive documentation including the curation workflow, hands-on notebooks, helper functions, and extension classes to support practical usages.

All software components in the topo4d ecosystem are released under the Apache-2.0 license. The 4D-WORKS online documentation is provided under the MIT license. The accompanying demo datasets are shared under the CC-BY-4.0 license.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

This pilot project introduces a STAC-based metadata management framework for topographic 4D datasets and proposes the topo4d extension to explicitly curate time-dependent information such as reference epochs, alignment uncertainty and transformation matrices. The strength of embedding the topo4d extension in the established STAC framework lies particularly in the possibility to curate complex multi-source and multi-temporal datasets from a range of sensors (LiDAR, photogrammetry, multispectral, radar) and platforms (ground-based, airborne, satellite) for integrated spatiotemporal analysis in environmental monitoring scenarios. While highly innovative for the curation of in-situ 4D datasets, the integration with the established framework makes optimal use of existent frameworks that are already used or easily accessible for the community. By showcasing the topo4d extension with real-world catalogs of multi-source riverbed monitoring and high-frequency long-term sandy beach monitoring, we demonstrate that heterogeneous topographic 4D datasets can be organized with an easily accessible and flexible tool towards a more interoperable, reusable manner following the FAIR principle.

III. Challenges and Gaps

Metadata curation and management for multi-source topographic 4D datasets remains challenging, as information not explicitly supported in existing formats is easily neglected or lost during manual data curation. Current strategies, adhering to best practices, typically use unstructured text files or supplementary documents that are tedious to parse and maintain. Our proposed STAC-based framework addresses these limitations by preserving metadata in a machine-readable, extensible, hierarchical form that connects topographic 4D datasets with other STAC-compliant resources, such as established satellite imagery time series STAC catalogs or photogrammetry items. This interoperability provides the basis for integrated spatiotemporal analysis across spatiotemporal scales. The (Geo)JSON-based modular structure of STAC supports integration with existing geospatial data processing tools and enables systematic curation of common, acquisition, processing, time-dependent, and assets metadata. The topo4d extension em-

phasizes the importance of temporal evolution and cross-epoch relationships, enhancing the functionality of STAC for comprehensive topographic 4D datasets.

Practical challenges still exist in curating and cataloging topographic 4D datasets with our proposed schema. A key consideration is how to distinguish between metadata and auxiliary data, as auxiliary information (e.g., maps, derived features, masks, thumbnails) may also serve as asset instances within a catalog. Defining consistent and transparent rules for curating metadata is important for maintaining semantic clarity and reproducibility. These rules tend to rely on prior experiences or specific applications. Therefore, data curators remain responsible for carefully designing case-specific metadata strategies. Looking ahead, topographic 4D data management should treat time-dependent metadata as a core and explicit component of dataset creation. The proposed extension and workflow provide a foundation for systematically curating and cataloging metadata with increased interoperability and reusability. By fostering consistent practices across tools and repositories, the topo4d extension contributes to a more unified and FAIR approach to documenting and sharing topographic 4D data.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

Expected users are scientists and data curators who benefit from our proposed metadata framework both when acquiring and processing own data more efficiently as well as when using published data, which so far can often be integrated in own workflows only by preparing tailored scripts in a first step. The latter is also highly relevant for university teachers, where diversification of use cases, e.g., in practical courses is strongly facilitated by using harmonized (meta)data. Infrastructure providers, such as data repositories, can use the standard and workflow as instrument to perform technical checks on submitted data, and importantly, to provide guidelines/requirements for publishers of 3D time series data. Through the integration with STAC and the possibility to couple a range of data sources (3D and imagery, in-situ to satellite) within a catalog, the topo4d framework also facilitates increasingly relevant research directions of combining spatiotemporal scales through fusion and integrated analysis. Ultimately, the metadata standard and curation workflow benefit all end users (including public authorities and decision makers) who rely on transparent and reproducible workflows to further process and interpret information derived from 4D data in Earth observation and environmental monitoring.

Our topo4d extension and 4D-WORKS workflow will be distributed through a half-day tutorial session (Figure 6) during the 25th ISPRS Congress 2026⁹, in which researchers and students from the photogrammetry and remote sensing fields will learn the concepts and workflow of 4D metadata management. The workshop material will be released as open-source material, so that future users can benefit from the training at any given time.

⁹ <https://www.isprs2026toronto.com/>

Sunday, 5 July, 2026

8:30am - 12:00pm

Tutorial Lead:

Jiapan Wang

Co-Instructors:

Xiaoyu Huang

Katharina Anders

Advanced Topographic Time Series Data Management Using the Topo4d Extension of the Spatiotemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) for Curation, Analysis, and Visualization of 4D Point Clouds

Half Day (4 Hours)

4D point cloud datasets, which capture changes in 3D over time, are becoming increasingly important across a broad range of applications, including environmental and infrastructure monitoring. As data sharing grows and diverse tools and methods become more widely available, the need for standardized approaches to managing time-dependent metadata becomes more critical too.

This tutorial introduces participants to the challenges and solutions involved in handling multi-temporal 3D data, with a focus on automation, interoperability, and integration with existing tools.

Participants will learn how to harmonize and automate the creation of time-dependent metadata using the open-source topo4d framework — a recent extension of the well-established Spatiotemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) standard. The tutorial will cover how to generate, read, and integrate metadata from diverse topographic data sources, regardless of acquisition method or temporal resolution. Emphasis will be placed on aligning with best practices to ensure metadata reusability and consistency across projects.

Through hands-on sessions, participants will incorporate the topo4d workflow into existing 4D data pipelines and connect it with widely used tools such as PDAL and the py4dgeo Python library for change analysis. A key use case will demonstrate the benefits of this standardized approach for applications in geomorphology, hydrology, and ecology.

By the end of the tutorial, attendees will be equipped with practical tools, clear guidelines, and example datasets to streamline their own 4D processing workflows — enhancing reproducibility and collaboration in the Earth science community.

[Read less](#)

Figure 6 Introduction of the tutorial session to be held during the 25th ISPRS Congress 2026.

V. Future Directions

Future work and recommended directions can be divided into three aspects: short-term plans, mid-term goals, and long-term visions.

In short-term plans, development will focus on strengthening the integration of topo4d within the broader STAC ecosystem and improving usability for researchers. This includes extending the Python toolkit with additional helper functions, validation utilities, and converters to ensure seamless use of the topo4d extension alongside established STAC clients and APIs. Practical integration pathways with analysis software such as PDAL, CloudCompare, py4dgeo, and pointcloudset will be expanded to enable automatic reading and writing of topo4d-compliant metadata during typical processing workflows. Additionally, more hands-on examples and tutorials will be added to support early adoption and provide guidance for applying the workflow to different data ecosystems (<https://www.isprs2026toronto.com/tutorial-session-information>).

For the mid-term goals, the focus will shift toward building community services and collaborative infrastructures that support the exchange and reuse of curated 4D catalogs. Findability and accessibility would be the focus in this stage, particularly through the establishment of a STAC-based catalog hosting, either within NFDI4Earth or in cooperation with existing data repositories

(e.g., PANGAEA). This will enable the publication, discovery, and harvesting of topo4d catalogs via stable endpoints. This would include out-of-box hosting of curated topographic 4D datasets from ongoing monitoring campaigns, as well as automated ingestion pipelines that apply the curation workflow to new data.

In the long term, the ambition is to enable a fully interconnected ecosystem of topographic 4D data that is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable across institutions and scientific domains. This includes advancing topo4d extension from a standalone extension into a widely accepted community standard embedded within major geospatial tools, repositories, and analysis pipelines. Ultimately, the vision is an end-to-end RDM workflow in which acquisition, processing, metadata curation, catalog publication, and analytical interpretation are seamlessly connected, ensuring that topographic 4D datasets become as easily accessible and reusable as typical spatiotemporal Earth observation datasets. This would reinforce FAIR-aligned practices across the geosciences and lay the groundwork for sustained, collaborative, and cross-domain 4D data infrastructures.

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